

Full Research Paper

Beyond "lab washing": A methodology for social impact assessment in Living Labs

Authors

Gregor Cerinšek¹, Vaike Fors², Melania Mihalcea²

¹ Halmstad University, Kristian IV:s väg 3, Halmstad, Sweden / Institute for Innovation and Development of the University of Ljubljana, Kongresni trg 12, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

² Halmstad University, Kristian IV:s väg 3, Halmstad, Sweden.

Abstract

This article introduces a process-oriented assessment methodology designed to address persistent challenges in Living Lab practice, such as lab-washing, social impact assessment, and assuring long-term, value-driven transformation and sustainability. Grounded in design ethnographic practice and embedding iterative and participatory engagements, the approach enables continuous reflection and adaptation rooted in real-life Living Lab contexts. Key methods – such as ethnographic deep dives, trading zones, Think Forward workshops, and assessment interviews – enable the identification of both intended and emergent social impacts while fostering community ownership and deep scaling. The article argues that embedding assessment throughout the lifecycle of a Living Lab enhances its credibility, strengthens collaboration across project streams, and better supports systemic change. In doing so, it offers a practical framework for moving beyond symbolic participation and toward authentic, context-sensitive transformation, specifically within EU-funded projects' contexts.

Key words

Design ethnography, social impact, process-oriented assessment, living lab, deep scaling

Introduction

Irrespective of the growing adoption of Living Lab model into major EU initiatives and funding programmes (ENoLL, 2025, p. 29, 32) one of the key challenges also central for this article is how to move beyond short-term, pragmatic goals and outcomes to foster long-term, value-driven transformation that is embedded in socio-political contexts and sustainable beyond a specific project and its funding (Bhatta et al., 2025; Smith & Iversen, 2018). As Living Labs become increasingly institutionalised in EU policy frameworks, their conceptual diffusion risks turning them into what Lévi-Strauss (1987) calls “floating signifiers”, i.e., terms stripped of substance but retained for their rhetorical power. Our prior ethnographic research (Cerinšek, 2024; Cerinšek & Podjed, 2024) suggests that this is often driven by pressure to conform to the formal criteria of EU funding calls, which valorise keywords like co-creation and iterative bottom-up innovation while neglecting the depth of authentic practice. This is in line with the so-called phenomenon of “lab-washing” (Joost et al., 2025, p. 5; Wrangsten, 2021), where concepts like participatory design and multi-stakeholder engagement are invoked more for their symbolic appeal rather than representing meaningful innovation spaces.

The challenge of lab-washing often arises from the misclassification of projects that, while demonstrating certain impacts, still adhere to conventional linear development models (research → design → test → implement) and traditional waterfall approaches, where user requirements are fixed in advance and each phase is executed sequentially. Projects tend to follow small-scale, rigid timelines, measuring success through IT artefacts and systems rather than knowledge production or “deep scale” community transformation (Moore et al., 2015). This narrow problem-solution mindset oversimplifies systemic challenges, marginalizes diverse perspectives, and overlooks the socio-political contexts in which innovation should be embedded. Consequently, such initiatives often struggle to sustain and scale beyond specific project funding, leading to the loss of depth, sustainability, long-term social impact, and transformative potential (von Wirth et al., 2019).

Closely linked to the “lab-washing” lies another structural challenge of EU projects. At the outset, the project consortium defines measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in the project application, outlining the targets that the living labs need to achieve throughout the project’s duration. These KPIs serve as guiding principles around which the evaluation is structured, as the difference between the baseline (before living lab interventions) and final measurements (after project delivery) is attributed to the living lab. The European Union as funder seeks evidence of the value of their investments to society; therefore, the achievement of the KPIs is considered a critical factor in measuring the

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

overall success of the project. Consequently, as argued by Reed et al. (2021, p. 2), there is a normative assumption underlying the broader “impact agenda” that projects should seek positive impacts rather than negative ones. As described by Cerinsek & Podjed (2024), the pre-defined KPIs (as project requirements) can drive a strong focus on finding positive examples and evidence that support and confirm the KPIs, potentially leading to confirmation bias (Nickerson, 1998). This occurs because the pressure to meet the KPIs can overshadow a more objective and scientific assessment and evaluation of living lab and project outcomes. The desire to fulfil KPI criteria and overall project objectives may, either intentionally or unintentionally, distort the interpretation of assessment results, resulting in a bias towards perceiving them as contributing factors, regardless of their actual merit (Cerinsek & Podjed, 2024, p. 1222).

In the context of impact assessment and evaluation, we argue that the structural challenge of confirmation bias – seeking or interpreting evidence in ways that support the anticipated impacts – often elevates randomized control trials, with their focus on quantitative methods, to the top of the living lab evaluation and assessment hierarchy (Reed et al., 2021, Hodson et al., 2023). While these can be appropriate for assessing clearly attributable impacts in controlled settings, they are often ill-suited to the complex, iterative, and non-linear nature of Living Labs, where causality is shaped by a web of interdependent processes and actors. As noted by Reed et al. (2021) there is no shortage of methods for assessing impacts (see for instance the overview from Overdiek and Genova, 2021); however, the challenge lies in choosing the most appropriate assessment methods to embrace living lab complexity, uncertainty, fluidity, and iteration, requiring continuous formative adaptation rather than one-size-fits-all solutions. The pathways to impact (i.e., living lab engagement activities that facilitate impacts) are continuously negotiated and shaped throughout the participatory process itself, making it particularly challenging (and sometimes even contradictory) when a living lab must adhere to a predefined project application or grant agreement, as required through EU-funded programmes (Cerinsek & Podjed 2024).

To address the twin challenges of lab-washing and inadequate impact assessment, this article expends on research-in-progress from the 2024 Open Living Lab Days conference (see Cerinsek et al., 2024), exploring the following research question: *How can a tailored assessment method grounded in collaborative, co-creative, and ethnographic paradigms support and structure Living Lab practices to promote long-term transformation and mitigate lab-washing tendencies?* In response – and as the article’s core contribution – we propose a process-oriented and context-sensitive methodology for assessing and

sustaining social impacts in Living Labs, developed through our design ethnographic work and collaborative orchestration of Living Labs within the EU-funded Horizon Europe GREEN-LOG project (2022, 2023, 2024). GREEN-LOG aims to develop Logistics-as-a-Service platforms for interconnected city logistics, combining autonomous delivery systems, cargo-bike micro-consolidation, and multimodal parcel solutions integrated with public transport. The approach is deployed and validated in five living labs: Athens, Barcelona, Flanders (cities of Ghent, Leuven, and Mechelen), Oxfordshire, and Ispra.

After the introductory section, the next chapter presents the theoretical foundations of the proposed process-oriented methodology, drawing primarily on a design ethnographic approach to service design (Smith et al., 2024; Fors et al., 2022; Ebbesson et al., 2024; Karakikes et al., 2025). The third chapter outlines the developed process-oriented assessment methodology and describes its implementation in the GREEN-LOG project (2022, 2023, 2024) which is then further discussed in the fourth chapter. The article concludes by summarizing the main outcomes.

Theoretical Foundations

In the social innovation and systemic change literature, the orientation toward enduring, qualitative transformation is referred to as "deep scaling" (Moore et al., 2015; Fraser, 2023) i.e., the meaningful embedding of innovation within communities and systems to transform cultural values, norms, interpersonal relationships, and collective worldviews. This approach is distinguished from "scaling out" – the replication or dissemination of innovations across broader populations or contexts; and "scaling up" – which pertains to influencing institutional policies and systemic structures. Rather than prioritising breadth or structural reach, "scaling deep" emphasises the cultivation of deeply rooted, context-specific change within communities and prioritises contextual specificity over generalisability. Although scaling has long been a focus in Living Lab projects, particularly in extending insights beyond their original context, scholarly interest has largely centred on "scaling out" or "scaling up" (von Wirth et al., 2019).

In the context of Living Labs, deep scaling has been evidenced through design ethnographic practices (Pink et al., 2022). Grounded in qualitative and interpretive inquiry, design ethnographic Living Labs enable close work with local stakeholders as agents of change (rather than passive recipients), eliciting situated knowledge to be used in co-design of both methodological tools and practical interventions that aligns with local values and lived experiences (cf. Fors et al., 2022, Ebbesson et al., 2024, Weberg et al., 2025).

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

The tailored deep scaling Living Lab assessment approach – presented in this article – is structured according to Smith & Iversen’s (2018) theoretical framework that emphasizes both the horizontal (local aspects of social, technical and organisational engagements), and vertical aspects (engagement with multiple levels of authority) of “participatory infrastructuring” (Bødker et al., 2017) for extending projects beyond their limited timelines. Rather than prescribing specific tools or methods, they propose three dimensions of engagement – scoping, developing, and scaling – which emphasize key aspects and qualities that can guide emerging participatory design practices aimed at fostering sustainability, long-term commitment, and meaningful social change.

Initially introduced as dimensions of engagement within participatory design, we – in our role of orchestrators of the GREEN-LOG (2022, 2023, 2024) Living Labs – began to adapt this conceptual structure into a phased framework to guide and assess Living Lab practices more systematically (see Figure 1). The initial “scoping phase” establishes a space of mutuality in which diverse participants collaboratively explore possible futures and align emerging aspirations, shifting from a model of limited stakeholder involvement to the cultivation of “protagonist communities”, i.e., stakeholders who take an active, often grassroots role in initiating and sustaining change (Smith & Iversen, 2018; GREEN-LOG, 2023). This phase often precedes and exceeds the temporal boundaries of conventional participatory design, allowing time for co-exploration and the emergence of unforeseen priorities and research questions. In the subsequent “developing phase”, the emphasis moves away from the creation of technological artefacts as fixed solutions towards the co-development of new understandings and practices, recognising that meaningful innovation arises not merely through tools, but through situated, socially embedded processes (Smith & Iversen, 2018). Finally, the “scaling phase” redefines impact not in terms of tangible deliverables but through the co-creation of strategies for enduring social change. Rather than imposing generalised outcomes, this approach foregrounds stakeholder-led negotiations around sustainability and impact, privileging ongoing, contextualised processes over predefined solutions.

Furthermore, our process-oriented methodology (described in the next chapter) is grounded in the premise that effectively identifying and understanding the social impacts of Living Labs requires more than assessing their final outcomes – such as produced solutions, products, or services, and their ultimate “end-of-pipe” impacts. Instead, it calls for continuous examination of the processes that shape these outcomes and also the intermediate impacts that emerge along the “pathway to impact” (Cerinsek et al., 2024;

Reed et al., 2021). To this end, the methodology is based on the ongoing co-exploration of the six foundational characteristics of Living Labs, as defined by ENoLL (2025, p. 21): active user involvement, multi-stakeholder participation, orchestration, co-creation, real-life settings, and a multi-method approach.

Thus, the process-oriented assessment approach not only enables continuous monitoring of impacts but also has the potential to estimate the impacts arising from evidence-based processes and interventions (as also argued by Reed et al., 2021 in their analysis of impact assessment frameworks and methods). In our context, this means that living labs that are capable of demonstrating and evidencing the alignment of their processes and activities with key living lab characteristics (ENoLL 2025, p. 21) are also more likely to develop outcomes and solutions that are deeply aligned with the needs and aspirations of the communities, thereby increasing the likelihood of achieving meaningful social impacts. In line with the theoretical foundations of the evidence synthesis evaluation approach (Reed et al., 2021), our process-oriented methodology is grounded in a logic model, which hypothesizes that an ideal living lab – one that adheres to key living lab characteristics (ENoLL 2025, p. 21) – also possesses the capacity to generate social impacts.

Process-oriented methodology for assessing social impacts in living labs

The GREEN-LOG project (2022, 2023, 2024) was designed to develop context-specific urban logistics solutions within Living Labs, involving stakeholders from local communities, municipal authorities, and logistics service providers. These Living Lab initiatives are supported by the project through the development of a data-driven platform and targeted assistance in establishing and operationalizing the Living Labs themselves. Our role in the project encompassed both: the establishment and orchestration of the Living Labs' development, and, secondly, the design of an accompanying methodology to assess their social Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), namely: (1) increased public awareness of sustainable urban delivery solutions; (2) acceptance of sustainable urban delivery solutions; and (3) improved neighbourhood life quality.

As the Living Lab methodology was co-created and tailored to support the overarching goal of establishing dynamic spaces for dialogue and shared understandings, it aligned closely with Smith and Iversen's (2018) framework of three interrelated dimensions of engagement in participatory design for sustainable change (see previous Chapter 2). This

methodological integration enabled us not only to facilitate the emergence of the Living Labs themselves but also to embed a process-oriented assessment approach from the outset.

Establishing and Orchestrating

Figure 1 illustrates the iterative stages undertaken during the first two years of the GREEN-LOG project, structured according to a conventional service design cycle comprising the phases of ‘understanding – defining – designing – evaluating’. The development of logistic solutions within the project is organized through two demonstrations, implemented in the second and third years respectively.

The initial iterative cycle – spanning months 0–12 – facilitated the formation of the Living Labs via a tailored scoping engagement process, the specifics of which are detailed in the next subchapter and Tables 1–3 in the Appendix (see also Cerinsek et al., 2024). This phase culminated in a series of scoping activities focused on the definition of solution blueprints and use cases. These, in turn, informed the second cycle (Months 12–24), during which a revised iteration of Living Lab requirements was undertaken as well as co-creative activities around mock-ups, prototypes and activity diagrams as prompts that enabled engagement in developing. This process culminated in the first demonstration of the proposed solutions, carried out over a four-month period across the various Living Lab settings. This initiated the next iterative cycle aimed at refining the solutions during the second demonstration phase, while also creating opportunities to engage with the scaling dimensions of these solutions.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Figure 1. Evolution of the process-oriented assessment methodology through iterative service design cycles of scoping, developing, and scaling.

Through this iterative approach, a process-oriented assessment methodology was developed – emerging from a tailored service design framework and, furthermore, informed by ethnographic insights into the social contexts of the various GREEN-LOG Living Labs that were shaped by the engagements undertaken during their establishment and initial orchestration. Based on this tailored process, assessment is conceived as a continuous practice of gathering, analysing, and interpreting data to understand key aspects of Living Lab activities and the significance, reach, and attribution of their outcomes. Crucially, assessment serves not as a static endpoint but as a tool for ongoing reflection, informed decision-making and adaptive governance throughout the three phases, enabling Living Lab teams to operate in a learning-oriented mode. Generated insights are systematically captured and synthesized using a combination of structured templates, cross-case thematic analysis, and internal feedback loops. These insights are regularly shared with Living Lab teams through dedicated reflection sessions and project group meetings, resulting in the re-prioritization of activities, adjustments to engagement strategies, or refinement of solution prototypes. This iterative reflection process allowed the Living Labs to shift direction when needed while maintaining alignment with their long-term social impact goals (illustrated in Figure 1).

Furthermore, our assessment approach is grounded in the principles of "deep scaling" (Moore et al., 2015), which we argue are particularly pertinent in Living Lab contexts. As an outcome of a process-oriented assessment methodology, "deep scaling" moves beyond surface-level implementation of solutions to examine how innovations become embedded in everyday practices, shaping values, narratives, routines, and relationships. Figure 2 provides a schematic representation of the developed process-oriented assessment methodology and its relationship to the iterative service design approach employed within the project.

Figure 2. A schematic presentation of the developed processual assessment methodology.

Insights gathered through iterative scoping, developing, and scaling engagements were not only used to assess progress but also informed revisions to the process-oriented model and specific engagement strategies for establishing the Living Lab networks of different actors. As part of our commitment to reflective practice, the model was adjusted after each iteration. For example, the initial 'scoping phase' highlighted the need for more scoping activities among stakeholder clusters as well as deeper understandings of how to bring the users into the development process. This led to the introduction of tools that enabled mapping of stakeholder engagement in the LLs, user stories and user journeys (see figure 1 and Table 2).

Similarly, midterm misalignments between social, technical, and logistical work streams prompted a recalibration of the co-design workshops to establish clearer connections between ethnographic insights and system requirements. In response, Living Lab

workshops were staged in which stakeholders collaboratively revisited and reiterated user journeys within the developed use cases. These sessions aimed to identify both known and unknown user needs, contextual barriers, and success criteria from the users' perspective. Additionally, participants were encouraged to reflect on how the envisioned services should function to be considered successful in real-life use.

The workshops culminated in the creation of action plans outlining strategies for investigating unknowns through further user studies and for tweaking and adapting technological solutions to the specificities of each Living Lab context. Importantly, this process helped technical partners recognize not only the impracticality of designing a one-size-fits-all solution, but also that user requirements are inherently shaped by local social and cultural conditions. In this way, the process-oriented nature of the model supports formative and proactive identification of emerging tensions, enabling adaptive responses during implementation, rather than relying solely on post-hoc evaluation.

The next subsections present the deep scaling activities and specific methods developed and applied within the GREEN-LOG project as core components of our process-oriented assessment approach.

Creating a qualitative baseline

Our scoping phase involved two iterations to establish a living lab “protagonist community” (Smith & Iversen 2018) together with an overall participatory framework (see Figure 1). The first iteration involved engaging with GREEN-LOG living lab stakeholders and facilitating co-creative activities to jointly articulate local requirements, barriers, and opportunities; exploring potential futures and social impacts; synthesizing diverse goals, interests, and agendas into a common vision; and develop strategies aligned with the objectives and aspirations of the GREEN-LOG living labs (see Cerinsek et al., 2024, p. 306-307). It also implied the crucial task of identifying the core project team stakeholders, the involved team, and the informed team in each living lab, as well as pointing out the physical areas in which the delivery solutions would be developed.

From a methods perspective, the scoping phase implemented two iterations of digital co-design workshops – i.e., the first Meet-Up (see Table 1 in Appendix) and the second Meet-Up (see Table 2 in Appendix) –, as well as scoping interviews with living lab stakeholders between both iterations to collect additional qualitative data regarding the future of the living labs (see Table 3 in Appendix). While the first co-design iteration focused on assessing the existing barriers and seizing opportunities within the living labs, the second

iteration identified the specific requirements of various user types involved in the use case scenarios for delivery solutions in each living lab, including customers, drivers, operational managers, shopkeepers, policy makers, and the broader citizens. In addition to detailing living lab users and their known and unknown needs, the results of the second iteration aim to describe contextual specifics and establish a focus for further user engagement and assessment studies that address these uncertainties. It produced a list of key requirements for each living lab, along with a list of common, more general friction points encountered in implementing these types of delivery solutions (see also Cerinsek et al., 2024, p. 308-309).

These activities established a qualitative baseline for the process-oriented assessment methodology – serving as a co-created point of departure that Living Lab stakeholders could revisit and reflect upon throughout the subsequent stages of the assessment.

Re-assessment and Reality-check

The established baseline from the scoping phase informed the assessment framework in the so called “re-assessment” phase, aiding to identify key recurring themes, issues, and specific social impact sub-categories, as well as understanding contextual differences and similarities between the living labs. Similarly to the Scoping, this stage involved conducting “re-assessment” interviews (see Table 4 in Appendix) with living lab stakeholders; both those involved in the scoping phase and new participants who joined later.

Additionally, co-design “trading zones” were organized, bringing together different stakeholders across the five GREEN-LOG living labs. We define “trading zone” as a collaborative space where diverse living lab stakeholders come together to interact and exchange (“trade”) their knowledge, ideas, and past experiences, despite their differences and without being hampered of conflicting interests and agendas (see also Kemman, 2021; GREEN-LOG, 2023, p. 11). These trading zones provided an opportunity to jointly reflect on living lab progress from a social perspective, assess social key performance indicators, exchange insights on stakeholder and user engagement, and build capacity and specific ways of creating, assessing and sustaining social impacts (see Table 5 in Appendix).

Think forward

The "Think Forward" phase represents the culminating scaling stage of the process-oriented assessment methodology, serving both as a reflective synthesis and a forward-looking space for strategic planning. Anchored in design ethnographic principles, the "Think forward" workshops are structured to support collective foresight, enabling living lab stakeholders to envision plausible futures, negotiate shared commitments, and identify pathways for institutional anchoring and policy alignment. This also provides an opportunity to collectively assess whether and to what extent the envisioned social Key Performance Indicators have been achieved across the pilot sites.

Importantly, this phase is not only evaluative but generative: by reflecting on lessons learned, evolving stakeholder dynamics, and emerging local narratives, participants can formulate strategies for embedding outcomes more deeply into their institutions and communities. In this sense, Think Forward workshops are crucial enablers of deep scaling (Moore et al., 2015). They foster a transition from project-centred intervention to community-rooted transformation, ensuring that the value created through Living Lab activities extends beyond the formal project lifecycle.

Ethnographic Deep Dives

In addition to already described methods, the process-oriented methodology includes an ongoing implementation of "deep dives", i.e., ethnographic explorations into the everyday practices, routines, and dynamics of the living labs. These deep dives are carried out by anthropologists who conduct site visits to specific GREEN-LOG living labs, immersing themselves in the local contexts. The aim is to capture the "Spirit of place" (Chamberlain et al., 2018) by gaining rich and genuine qualitative insights into the lived experiences of diverse participants, while also uncovering the nuances of their daily routines and the social, cultural, and physical contexts in which the living labs are embedded. A range of qualitative methods are used, including open discussions, informal conversations, participant observation, and semi-structured interviews, allowing researchers to gather thick data (Geertz, 1973; Wang, 2016) from various sources and perspectives.

To capture lived experiences in more embodied ways (Roberts, 2020), additional methods such as sensory walks and sensory bike rides are employed, in which stakeholders and citizens guide researchers through their everyday routes and reflect on their environment, routines, and perceptions along the way (Murray & JärviLuoma, 2019; Abram & Bajic, 2022). These engagements not only reveal hidden frictions and unspoken needs but also open space for empathy-building between different user groups and project partners.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

OPEN
LIVING
LAB
DAYS

Photo documentation and co-creative filmmaking (Mihalcea et al., 2024) are also integrated, enabling us to express diverse experiences visually and narratively (see Photos 1-4).

Practically, these deep dives are structured as short, intensive field visits, usually lasting two to three days and designed to be flexible enough to integrate into the fast-paced rhythm of everyday life. They require close collaboration with local living lab coordinators, who help identify participants, set up meetings, and mediate access to relevant spaces. These engagements offer a high return in insight, often surfacing latent issues or alternative perspectives that would be difficult to uncover through other conventional assessment methods. Most importantly, they help ensure that the process of co-creation remains grounded in real-life experiences, fostering a more nuanced understanding of the social impacts that emerge along the pathway to implementation.

Photos 1-4: Sensory bike rides and co-creative filmmaking in Flanders and Oxfordshire

Discussion

This article set out to explore the research question: *How can a tailored assessment method grounded in collaborative, co-creative, and ethnographic paradigms support and structure Living Lab practices to promote long-term transformation and mitigate lab-washing tendencies?* Building on Smith & Iversen’s (2018) framework and Moore et al.’s (2015) concept of “deep scaling”, the process-oriented assessment methodology was designed to embed both horizontal (local socio-technical and organizational engagement) and vertical (institutional and policy-level engagement) dimensions of participatory infrastructuring across all phases:

- **Scoping Phase:** This phase emphasized horizontal engagement by surfacing local knowledge, goals, and needs. It supported vertical alignment by initiating dialogue with municipal authorities early on, laying the groundwork for institutional anchoring. In terms of deep scaling, it focused on building “protagonist communities” and nurturing shared ownership, which are prerequisites for shifting values and long-term transformation.
- **Developing Phase:** Horizontal engagement deepened as users, community groups, and logistics actors co-developed and iterated on service concepts through prototyping and mock-ups. Vertical integration was supported through feedback loops between living lab actors and decision-makers, ensuring that local insights could influence broader implementation frameworks. This phase contributed to deep scaling by embedding co-creation practices into routine development workflows, gradually shifting how stakeholders collaborated and valued different forms of expertise.
- **Scaling Phase:** Vertical aspects were emphasized most strongly here, exploring institutional uptake and policy translation. Horizontally, communities were involved in assessing impacts and envisioning future adaptations. Deep scaling was fostered by encouraging stakeholders to imagine long-term futures beyond the project’s lifecycle, enabling cultural and institutional embedding of the Living Lab innovations.

Our practical experiences and research findings suggest that the proposed process-oriented assessment methodology offers an alternative to the linear, quantitative-driven evaluation models that often dominate EU-funded innovation projects. By aligning assessment with participants’ lived experiences and fostering ongoing reflection, the approach safeguards against lab-washing by ensuring that participation is authentic and contextually grounded rather than merely symbolic.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

While the scoping phase was initially successful – with all Living Labs actively engaged and aligned with the participatory nature – challenges emerged during the later stages, particularly after a six-month period in which the focus shifted to technological development. As Smith & Iversen (2018, p. 32) also note, exploratory activities can be inherently uncertain, messy, and disruptive, especially when their outputs are not immediately translatable into conventional development terms. Although many living labs began the first exploration iteration with enthusiasm, during the intermediate period, several shifted their focus toward defining concrete technological requirements, which demanded clarity, specificity, and result-driven direction. Consequently, when the second round of co-creative exploration resumed, some participants were reluctant to re-engage with open-ended exploratory activities, perceiving them with scepticism. For instance, the technical partners expressed frustration that the processes did not produce the kind of fixed, detailed input typically expected in waterfall models of software development. As one participant noted, "We were just workshopping for the sake of workshopping." This disconnect underscores a key lesson: the success of Living Lab methodologies hinges not only on early stakeholder engagement but also on sustained alignment across diverse project work streams. Exploratory, participatory phases must be clearly communicated as integral to the broader development process – not as separate or secondary tasks – to avoid being perceived as redundant or misaligned with technical timelines.

The immersive approach of “deep dives” fostered a more profound understanding of the dynamic relationships between living lab solutions and technology, users, and the surrounding environments. It also enabled the identification of not only intended impacts, but also more intangible, unpredictable, unforeseen, subjective, and context-dependent social impacts; whether within or beyond the scope of the pre-defined KPIs. These types of impacts are often not anticipated during the project application phase and can be easily overlooked when relying solely on a top-down, summative evaluation approaches. In one case, a sensory walk through a residential neighbourhood revealed deep-rooted concerns among elderly residents about potential increase of delivery traffic and noise, issues that had not been raised in design workshops with living labs, therefore prompting them to engage more directly with vulnerable groups.

A key limitation and a missed opportunity encountered during the implementation of the ethnographic “deep dives” was the limited participation of technology developers. We argue that their direct involvement could have helped to ensure a more immediate and nuanced translation of social observations into technological specifications. Instead,

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

insights from the deep dives (and also participatory workshops to some extent) had to be relayed second-hand through reports and meetings, introducing potential delays and interpretation gaps. While these findings were eventually shared with the technology partners, their absence during the fieldwork meant they missed the opportunity for real-time immersion and direct experience of the local contexts. As a result, they were unable to fully grasp the atmosphere, rhythms, and specific social dynamics of the real physical places and their people. We claim that this lack of embodied understanding limited the immediacy of insights, hindered the development of a shared perspective with other stakeholders, and ultimately reduced the potential impact of the findings in terms of accurately assessing and responding to user requirements from a technological point of view.

Compared to conventional evaluation practices, the key distinctive added value of the process-oriented assessment methodology is that assessors are not merely independent "armchair" observers. Based on the implementation experiences we claim that the methodology aims to challenge the typical power dynamics between evaluators (in conventional terms) and those being evaluated by empowering and engaging stakeholders in the iterative processes from the very beginning, making the continuous formative assessment a natural and integral part of the overall living lab development. The approach enables these groups to actively shape the assessment and co-interpret the outcomes, rather than positioning them as passive research subjects to an external evaluator. In addition, the approach provided living lab stakeholders with formative feedback enabling them to learn from mistakes and to identify and ideally reduce negative outcomes during the pathway to impact.

This shift in evaluator role occasionally led to tensions regarding objectivity. Being part of the same project team can blur the lines between critical assessment and supportive project development, especially when team members are simultaneously involved in designing, implementing, and assessing activities. On one hand, this integrated role enhanced responsiveness, allowing assessors to provide real-time formative feedback that directly informs adjustments in development activities. On the other hand, it introduced the risk of "insider bias," where evaluators may (consciously or unconsciously) avoid surfacing negative findings, downplay tensions, or overemphasize successes in order to align with broader project goals (leading to "confirmation bias") or to simply maintain harmony within the team. To address this, the process-oriented methodology aims to employ different assessment methods (as presented in the previous chapter) and also triangulate the data sources to ensure a more balanced interpretation of findings.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

The methodological approach needs to generate a “contribution story” that also considers alternative explanations, offering an understanding of how and why certain impacts (did, could, should, or did not) occur. Ultimately, we claim that the value of embedded evaluation lies not in detachment, but in the ability to critically engage from within, provided that clear ethical boundaries and reflective practices are in place.

Conclusion

This article introduced a process-oriented, ethnographically informed assessment methodology tailored to the dynamics of Living Labs. Developed and applied within the Horizon Europe GREEN-LOG project, the approach responds to the dual challenge of promoting long-term social transformations while avoiding the pitfalls of lab-washing. It does so by embedding iterative, participatory assessment practices throughout the Living Lab lifecycle – emphasizing context sensitivity, stakeholder empowerment, and “deep scaling” over static models, which are often rooted in primarily quantitative evaluation approaches, and driven by predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and linear problem-solution development models.

While the proposed process-oriented assessment methodology offers a comprehensive framework, we acknowledge that its implementation in EU-funded contexts often faces real-world constraints such as limited project timelines, institutional resistance, and uneven stakeholder capacities. To enhance its transferability under such conditions, the approach emphasizes modular and scalable tools – such as structured co-design workshops, targeted interviews, and embedded reflection moments – that can be adapted to fit time-constrained or resource-limited settings. Its iterative structure allows for flexible entry points, ensuring that even partial application can generate value. Moreover, the presence of Living Lab facilitators and orchestrators is key to sustaining momentum, mediating between stakeholder groups, and ensuring that insights are not only gathered but also translated into adaptive decision-making. By explicitly designing for imperfect conditions, the methodology supports a realistic and grounded pathway toward adaptive governance and sustained social impact.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Acknowledgement

The authors of this article acknowledge that the work is part of the Horizon Europe GREEN-LOG project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101069892, and from the United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) agency. We also acknowledge the support of the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency in research program P2-0266. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), the UKRI, nor the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them. The authors would also like to thank the anonymous reviewers of Open Living Lab Days 2025 Conference whose comments significantly enhanced the quality of this article.

References

1. Abram, Sandi and Blaz Bajic (2022). Perception Against: Reflecting Ethnographically on the Sensory, Walking, and Atmospheric Turns. *Etnološka tribina*, 52(45), 112-126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15378/1848-9540.2022.45.04>
2. Bhatta, Astha, Heleen Vreugdenhil, and Jill Slinger (2025). A living lab learning framework rooted in learning theories. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 114, 1-12. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2025.107894>
3. Bødker, Susanne, Chistian Dindler, and Ole Sejer Iversen (2017). Tying knots: Participatory infrastructuring at work. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 26, 245-273. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10606-017-9268-y>
4. Cerinsek, Gregor and Dan Podjed (2024). "Parole, parole": Unveiling the narrative framework of EU research and innovation projects. *Politics & Policy*, 52(6), 1210-1226. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/polp.12636>
5. Cerinsek, Gregor, Vaike Fors, Melania Mihalcea, Michiel Bertels, Regina Enrich Sard (2024). 'How to stage and assess processes of co-creation in Living Labs: a design ethnographic approach'. In: *Proceedings of the OpenLivingLab Days Conference 2024: "living labs frontiers": driving systemic change through Soci(et)al Engagement, for real impact*. Brussels: European Network of Living Labs, ENoLL. Pp. 303-312.
6. Chamberlain, Kerry, Kathryn McGuigan, David Anstiss, Kayla Marshall (2018). A Change of View: Arts-Based Research and Psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 15(2-3), 131-139.
7. Ebbesson, Esbjörn, Jesper Lund, Vaike Fors & Rachel Charlotte Smith (2024). Design Ethnographic Toolkits in Living Labs. In: *Proceedings of the OpenLivingLab Days Conference 2024: "living labs frontiers": driving systemic change through Soci(et)al Engagement, for real impact*. Brussels: European Network of Living Labs, ENoLL. Pp. 313-328).
8. ENoLL (2025). Living Lab origins, developments and future perspectives. Published by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), 2025. D. Schuurman, M.I. DeLosRios-White, M. Desole (eds). Licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>.
9. Fors, Vaike, Meike Brodersen, Kaspar Raats, Sarah Pink & Rachel Charlotte Smith (2022). 'Investigating ADM in shared mobility: A Design Ethnographic approach'. In: S. Pink, M. Berg, D. Lupton & M. Ruckenstein (eds.), *Everyday Automation: Experiencing and Anticipating Automated Decision-Making*, pp. 197-212. Routledge.
10. Fraser, Tatiana (2023). The Art of Scaling Deep. Research in Summary. Ashoka: The Systems Sanctuary. Accessible at: <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5a0b2bbb80bd5e8ae706c73c/t/650e01c6fba1ac5ee2d1ae74/1729278091739/The+Art+of+Scaling+Deep+September+2023.pdf> (Accessed 12 March 2025).
11. Geertz, Clifford (1973). *The Interpretation of Cultures: Selected Essays*. New York: Basic Books.
12. GREEN-LOG (2022). Grant Agreement of the GREEN-LOG Horizon Europe Project (Project 101069892, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01).
13. GREEN-LOG (2023). Deliverable 1.1 – Knowledge Base of Last-mile Solutions and GREEN-LOG Requirements Specification. Deliverable of the GREEN-LOG Horizon Europe Project (Project 101069892, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01). Deliverable leader: University of Antwerp. Date of delivery: 25 June 2024.
14. GREEN-LOG (2024). Deliverable 1.3 – Assessment, Transferability and Adaptability Framework. Deliverable of the GREEN-LOG Horizon Europe Project (Project 101069892, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01). Deliverable leader: Halmstad University. Date of delivery: 30 June 2023.
15. Hodson, Elise, Teija Vainio, Michel Nader Sayún, Martin Tomitsch, Ana Jones, Meri Jalonen, Ahmet Börütecene, Md Tanvir Hasan, Irina Paraschivoiu, Annika Wolff, Sharon Yavo-Ayalon, Sari Yli-Kauhaluoma, and Gareth W. Young (2023). Evaluating Social Impact of Smart City Technologies and Services: Methods, Challenges, Future Directions. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, 7(3), 33, 1-32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti7030033>
16. Joost, Jan-Marc, Martin Lanzendorf and Tonio Weicker (2025). Mobility transition through labs in

- real-world contexts. The contribution of transdisciplinary approaches in creating sustainable transportation systems. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 124, 1-8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2025.104153>
17. Karakikes, Ioannis, Athena Tsimpa, Federico Moro, Vaike Fors, Amalia Polydoropoulou (2025). Piloting a joint delivery system of droids and cargo bikes at the JRC Ispra campus: A service design approach. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 110, pp. 1-17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2025.101541>
 18. Kemman, Max (2021). *Trading Zones of Digital History*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg.
 19. Lévi-Strauss, Claude (1987). *Introduction to the Work of Marcel Mauss*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
 20. Mihalcea, Melania, Vaike Fors, and Gregor Cerinsek (2024). 'Co-Creative filmmaking for integration of user perspectives in living lab environments'. In: *Proceedings of the OpenLivingLab Days Conference 2024: "living labs frontiers": driving systemic change through Soci(et)al Engagement, for real impact*. Brussels: European Network of Living Labs, ENoLL. Pp. 114-121.
 21. Moore, Michele-Lee, Darcy Riddell and Dana Vocisano (2015). Scaling Out, Scaling Up, Scaling Deep Strategies of Non-profits in Advancing Systemic Social Innovation. *The Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 58(67-84). DOI: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jcorpciti.58.67>
 22. Murray, Lesley and Helmi Järviuoma (2019). Walking as transgenerational methodology. *Qualitative Research*, 20(2), pp. 67-84. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794119830533>
 23. Nickerson, Raymond (1998). Confirmation Bias: A Ubiquitous Phenomenon in Many Guises. *Review of General Psychology*, 2(2), 175-220. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.2.2.175>
 24. Overdiek, Anja and Mari Genova (2021). Evaluating living labs? – an overview of existing methods and tools. White Paper, The Hague: The Hague University of Applied Sciences. Accessible at: https://www.thuas.com/sites/hhs/files/documents/Evaluation%20LL_Nov2021_Overdiek_Genova.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).
 25. Pink, S., Fors, V., Lanzeni, D., Duque, M., Sumartojo, S., & Strengers, Y. (2022). *Design Ethnography: Research, Responsibilities, and Futures*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003083665>
 26. Reed, Mark, Marrie Ferré, Julia Martin-Ortega, Rachel Blanche, Ruth Lawford-Rolfe, Martin Dallimer, Joseph Holden (2021). Evaluating impact from research: A methodological framework. *Research Policy*, 50(4), 1-14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104147>.
 27. Roberts, Simon (2020). *The Power of Not Thinking: How our Bodies Learn and Why we Should Trust Them*. London: 535.
 28. Smith, Rachel Charlotte and Ole Sejer Iversen (2018). Participatory design for sustainable social change. *Design Studies*, 59, 9-36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2018.05.005>
 29. Smith, Rachel Charlotte, Vaike Fors, Meike Brodersen, Jesper Lund & Esbjörn Ebbesson (2024). Sustainable Automated Futures: Participatory Human Approaches to Urban Mobility. In: Vaike Fors, Martin Berg, Meike Brodersen (Eds.), *The De Gruyter Handbook of Automated Futures: Imaginaries, Interactions and Impact*, pp. 413-434. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110792256-025>
 30. Wang, Tricia (2016). Why Big Data Needs Thick Data. *Ethnography Matters*. Accessible at: <https://medium.com/ethnography-matters/why-big-data-needs-thick-data-b4b3e75e3d7> (Accessed 12 March 2025).
 31. von Wirth, Timo, Lea Fuenfschilling, Niki Frantzeskaki, & Lars Coenen (2019). Impacts of urban living labs on sustainability transitions: Mechanisms and strategies for systemic change through experimentation. *European Planning Studies*, 27(2), pp. 229-257. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2018.1504895>
 32. Weberg, Oliver, Vaike Fors & Jesper Lund (2025). Scaling Deep with Local Community Champions in Living Labs. *Sustainability*, 17(13), 5888. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17135888>
 33. Wrangsten, Caroline (2021). Why does JPI Urban Europe not only fund but also develop the urban living labs approach? In European Urban Knowledge Network, *Urban Living Labs: Experimental Methods Drive Urban Transitions*. Available at: <https://eukn.eu/urban-voices/johannes-riegler-caroline-wrangsten-and-jonas-bylund-on-why-experimental-methods-drive-urban-transitions/> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

Appendix

Table 1. The aim, format, and the process of the first GREEN-LOG “Meet-Up”

Aim	Co-create living lab journey with a focus on goals, needs, barriers, opportunities, together with identifying key stakeholders and future activities
Format	Co-design workshop in a group setting – participants are members of one specific GREEN-LOG living lab
Process:	
(1) Introduction	Write the names and roles of meet-up participants. Present the living lab description as stated in the GREEN-LOG grant agreement. Present the GREEN-LOG task description that is related to the scoping phase (Requirements and living lab formulation approach), together with objectives, milestones, and deliverables. Present the evolution of a living lab concept (from testbeds, living labs and urban living labs to future smart living)
(2) Exploring goals and vision (guiding questions)	What do you want to achieve with your living lab? Who and what will benefit from the living lab? What are the primary challenges of the living lab? What is crucial for your living lab to succeed?
(3) Explore stakeholders (guiding questions)	Who are the main stakeholders of the Living Lab, and what role do they play? Are there any other critical stakeholders who would be beneficial to enrol? Why? Mapping out the stakeholders on the cluster map (Cluster A: Environmental and Community policy makers; Cluster B: Enablers of city logistics operations; Cluster C: Logistics & Technology; Cluster D: Local drivers, end-users, community-based organizations).
(4) Explore coming activities	What are your coming activities in the living lab? Vote and rank in order of importance, from most to least.
(5) Explore the innovation & design process	Position 5-6 of your prioritised activities for the Living Lab in the model: “Design for (expert and user-centred)” vs. “Design with (participatory co-design)” / “Insight (learn, problematize)” vs. “Validation (impact, adoption)”.
(6) Conclusion	What different steps do you need to take for realising your prioritised activities?

Table 2. The aim, format, and the process of the second GREEN-LOG “Meet-Up”

Aim	To initiate the development of an activity plan by identifying a core team and establishing a collaborative structure with involved and informed stakeholders, as well as identifying different users and mapping their potential user journeys when interacting with the proposed service.
Format	Co-design workshop in a group setting – participants are members from all GREEN-LOG living labs
Process:	

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

(1) Contextualizing	Mapping the implementation areas (insert a map with possible interaction points with people) Create user stories/proto personas (Who lives or works in the area that will use the service and why?)
(2) User Journey	Who are the main characters in your journey (description, title, age, needs, goals)? Identify scenario name Create journey steps: 1. When and where does your scenario play out?; 2. Inciting incident that gives your service a purpose to be used; 3. Key activities – What is being delivered, how is the service being used in this scenario step by step. 4. How does the service create value and meaning for the user?
(3) Journey Mapping	Mapping stakeholder engagement: 1. Core team, 2. Involved team, 3. Informed team Mapping living lab engagement activities: 1. What to do? 2. Where to do it? 3. How and who takes the lead? 4. With whom?

Table 3. The aim, format, and guiding questions of the “Scoping” Interviews

Aim	Explore living lab futures
Format	Individual interviews with living lab representatives
Guiding questions	
<p>Can you share your experiences with the GREEN-LOG project so far? How do you understand the concept of a living lab? What previous experiences have you had with living labs? What are your expectations for the GREEN-LOG living labs in the future? How do you envision organizing your collaboration within the living labs? In which part of your city would you like to implement the solutions, and why? What do you hope to learn from this living lab approach, both within your own living lab and across other living labs?</p>	

Table 4: The aim, format, and guiding questions of the “Re-assessment & Reality check” interviews

Aim	Re-assessment and Reality check
Format	Individually with living lab representatives
Themes and guiding questions	
(1) General Lessons Learned	<p>What have been the most significant lessons learned from your experience in the living lab? Are there any moments that stand out as particularly impactful or memorable?</p> <p>What practices or strategies worked particularly well working with empathizing, ideating and prototyping/implementing GREEN-LOG activities?</p> <p>How are lessons consolidated and shared within the living lab (internal stakeholders, citizens, etc.)?</p> <p>How are lessons consolidated and shared between the GREEN-LOG living labs?</p> <p>How are lessons consolidated and shared beyond the living labs?</p>

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

	What changes or improvements would you suggest for enhancing knowledge sharing processes within your living lab specifically and more broadly?
(2) Achievements & Success factors	What do you want to achieve with your Living Lab (specifically, what has changed since the Scoping phase)? What is crucial for your Living lab to succeed (specifically, what has changed since the Scoping phase)? Who and what will benefit from the Living Lab activities (specifically, what has changed since the Scoping phase)?
(3) Barriers & Challenges	What are the primary challenges of your Living lab? What did you experience as the primary barriers to implementing the GREEN-LOG activities (e.g., financial, technical, regulatory, stakeholder engagement, cultural)? Are these different than what was assessed in the Scoping phase? How have you navigated or overcome these challenges and barriers? Are there any stakeholder-specific challenges (e.g., community resistance, coordination issues)? How do you address resistance or conflicting priorities among stakeholders? Can you share examples of initiatives that did not work as planned in GREEN-LOG? What were the key takeaways?

Table 5. The setting, format, and guiding questions of the “Trading zones”

Aim	Reflect on living lab progress and explore ways of creating, assessing, and sustaining social impacts
Format	Co-design workshop in a group setting – participants are members from all GREEN-LOG living labs
Themes, objectives and guiding questions	
(1) Increased public awareness of sustainable urban delivery solutions	Objective: To assess the extent to which users and citizens are aware of sustainable urban logistics initiatives and solutions. How would you describe the public’s awareness of sustainable urban delivery solutions before and after the implementation of GREEN-LOG initiatives? What strategies have you used to raise awareness among stakeholders and citizens in general? Which have been the most effective? What are you still planning to implement? Have you conducted or participated in any outreach or communication campaigns? Have you observed any noticeable changes in how the public discusses or perceives sustainable urban logistics solutions? Are there any misconceptions or resistance to these solutions that you have encountered? How do you think they could be addressed? Have you collected any data to measure changes in awareness? If yes, what trends have you observed? If no, do you have any plans in place?
(2) Acceptance of sustainable urban delivery solutions	Objective: To jointly discuss and evaluate how willing businesses, citizens, and stakeholders are to adopt and support sustainable logistics solutions. What qualitative feedback have you received from stakeholders, businesses and residents regarding sustainable logistics solutions?

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

	<p>How have different stakeholders responded to the introduction of the sustainable logistics solutions? Have you noticed differences in acceptance among different demographic groups (e.g., age, profession, location)? What are the main barriers to acceptance that you have identified (e.g., trust, perceived inconvenience, cost concerns, etc.)? Have any stakeholders actively opposed or resisted the implementation of these solutions? If so, what were their concerns? Have you implemented any engagement activities to improve acceptance (e.g., involvement of users in co-design, pilot testing with users, incentive programs, etc.)? Do you have any data showing how acceptance has evolved over time? If no, do you have any plans in place?</p>
<p>(3) Improved neighbourhood life quality</p>	<p>Objective: Jointly determine whether GREEN-LOG innovations have positively impacted urban liveability.</p> <p>How do you measure improvements in neighbourhood life quality (e.g., surveys, traffic reduction, air quality data, resident feedback)? In general, do you think the public perceives these solutions as beneficial to their daily lives? Why or why not? Have you observed any changes in neighbourhood liveability since implementing sustainable urban logistics solutions (e.g., reduced noise, less congestion, improved air quality, etc.)? Have residents expressed any benefits or concerns regarding the logistics innovations in the city? Have you conducted or analysed any environmental or social impact assessments related to these initiatives? Have there been any unexpected positive or negative consequences of introducing these delivery solutions?</p>